

FISHER: Fully Integrated System for Handling, Evisceration, and Refinement of Tilapia Fish Establishing Potential Cobots Adaptation

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ABSTRACT

The FISHER cobot system (Fully Integrated System for Handling, Evisceration, and Refinement of Tilapia Fish, Establishing Potential Cobots Adaptation) presents an innovative approach to fish processing by integrating collaborative robotics (cobots) with advanced automation to enhance operational performance, worker safety, and product quality. This study aimed to design, develop, and evaluate an end-effector system for cleaning fish initial for tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), establishing potential collaborative robots (Cobot) adaptation to future high-value fish products' cleaning processes for enhanced safety. Utilizing a combination of hardware components—including an ATmega328P microcontroller, electric descaler, cutting tools, sensors, and a DOBOT CR3 collaborative robot— FISHER automates traditionally labor-intensive and hazardous tasks while maintaining precision and minimizing fish damage. The research methodology involved a mixed-methods approach, gathering quantitative data through comparative performance trials and statistical analysis using the Mann-Whitney U-Test, as well as qualitative feedback from industry practitioners via surveys and interviews. Results indicate that although manual processing currently remains faster ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$), the FISHER system significantly improves safety by reducing direct human contact with sharp instruments and repetitive strain while also offering comparable results based on qualitative feedback methods. The system's modular and programmable design demonstrates potential adaptability for more hazardous species, such as pufferfish or high-value fish, further emphasizing its industrial applicability. This thesis contributes a comprehensive framework for the integration of cobots in fish processing, advocating for safer, more efficient, and scalable automation solutions within the seafood industry.

Keywords: Collaborative robots, DOBOT-CR3, cobot end-effector, fish processing automation, seafood industry

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine fisheries sector, as reported by the Philippine Statistics Authority in 2022, produced 4.3 million metric tons of fish and fishery products—a 2.2% increase from the previous year. Aquaculture leads with over half the total production, and tilapia, particularly Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), is a major contributor, primarily produced in Central Luzon. As a key aquaculture commodity, tilapia plays a vital role in food security due to its adaptability and widespread consumer acceptance.

However, traditional fish processing techniques (TFPTs), deeply rooted in Philippine culture, face significant challenges. These methods often involve unsafe handling, increasing the risk of foodborne illnesses and physical injuries such as cuts, musculoskeletal disorders, and fatigue from repetitive labor. These factors compromise worker safety and product quality, prompting a need for safer and more efficient alternatives.

Robotics and automation are being introduced to modernize fish processing in the Philippines. Robotic solutions have been applied to tasks like cutting, slicing, and descaling, traditionally labor-intensive and injury prone. Collaborative robots, or Cobots, are especially valuable due to their safety features and ability to work directly with humans. Cobots are equipped with rounded edges, force limitations, and sensors to prevent accidents, making them suitable for precision tasks in food processing.

The FISHER system—Fully Integrated System for Handling, Evisceration, and Refinement—represents an innovative step in tilapia processing. This system incorporates a

collaborative robot, the DOBOT CR3, model DT-CR-6R030-001 which features a custom end-effector designed for handling, descaling, and eviscerating tilapia. While a human positions the fish, the robot performs precise cleaning and processing tasks, significantly reducing direct human contact and risk of injury. This ensures consistent quality and safer processing while maximizing meat yield.

The system has the potential to evolve further, possibly being adapted for hazardous fish species like pufferfish (Tetraodontidae), which contain the deadly tetrodotoxin. If proven effective, FISHER could revolutionize seafood processing by reducing occupational hazards and ensuring food safety.

Overall, the integration of collaborative robotics like FISHER into fish processing addresses long-standing health and efficiency issues in traditional methods. It paves the way for safer workplaces, higher-quality products, and the sustainable advancement of the Philippine seafood industry through smart automation. This aligns with global trends in food production, where robotics are enhancing output, hygiene, and precision in one of the most variable and labor-intensive sectors of the food industry.

METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

Hardware Design

Conceptual Framework

The figure below shows the conceptual framework of the prototype system. The inputs were derived from the study's objectives, which include designing a collaborative robot-based end-effector for safe tilapia processing, developing an integrated system with a collaborative robot (Cobot) for automated handling, and evaluating the system's performance and adherence to processing standards. The process was subdivided into four stages: hardware design, hardware development, software design, and software development. These stages focused on building and programming the prototype device to handle tasks such as scaling, evisceration, and safe interaction with humans. After going through the process, the expected output is a working system capable of fully processing tilapia fish through automated handling, descaling, and evisceration on a semi-autonomous platform.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework of the System

Figure 2 illustrates the initial end-effector design. This design incorporates a cutting blade, a refining descaler, and a microcontroller-based end-effector for fish handling. Specific components of the end-effector will be fabricated using 3D printing technologies available in the research location, specifically at the SMU-Technology Transfer and Business

Development Office (TTBDO). A motorized electric fish de-scaler and knife are integrated into the end-effector and controlled by microcontroller systems.

Figure 2
3D Model of FISHER System

Table 1 provides a comparative overview of current research on fish processing technologies, emphasizing the design and performance assessment of different fish processing equipment. The research concentrates on semi-automated and automatic systems exhibiting various features.

Table 1
Differentiation between Existing Related Studies and This Study FISHER

Feature	Design and Performance Evaluation of Semi-Automatic Fish Cutting Machine for Industry	Computer Vision Methods for Automating Turbot Fish Cutting	Design and construction of a fish descaling machine.	Automatic Fish Cutting and Cleaning Machine using Digital Image Processing	FISHER: Fully Integrated System for Handling, Evisceration, and Refinement of Tilapia Fish Establishing Potential Cobots Adaptation
	Kamaruzzaman, K.A, et al (2020)	Martin-Rodriguez, F, et. al (2022)	Abdelsamie, A.F(2019)	Bhuvaneswari, M, et al. (2019)	
Automatic cutting	Included	Included	Not included	Included	Included
Automatic de-scaling	Not included	Not included	Included	Included	Included
SMART sensor monitoring	Not included	Included	Not included	Included	Included
Mechanism	Industrial & Mechanical	Image & Video Processing	Mechanical	Digital Image Processing	Collaborative Robot
Test Application	Trout	Turbot	Tilapia	Catla & Silver Carp	Tilapia

Each study is evaluated based on processing duration, incorporation of automated cutting and de-scaling features, supplementary functionality such as pick and placing, smart sensor monitoring capabilities, labor requirements, and operational control simplicity. SMART sensor monitoring, which improves system intelligence and process oversight, is integrated into several systems, demonstrating technological breakthroughs. All systems are engineered to minimize human labor demands, indicating a substantial shift towards automation in the sector. Moreover, all assessed devices prioritize straightforward control procedures, guaranteeing user-friendly interfaces and enhanced usability. This review

emphasizes advancements in fish processing technologies and identifies prospects for more research and development.

Table 2
Analytical Framework for FISHER

STEP	DESCRIPTION	METHOD/TOOL	DATA SOURCE
Define Parameters	Identify key parameters: - performance - Safety - Quality	Literature review	Observations and analysis from research gaps and industry
Data Collection	Collect data on key parameters.	Quantitative and Qualitative Design	Direct observations, surveys, comparisons
Statistical Analysis	Analyze performance data before and after automation	Non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test Minitab software	Performance metrics
Qualitative Analysis	Assess worker and management feedback on automation's impact	Interview, direct observations, & documentations	Interview, direct observations, & documentations
Synthesis of Results	Combine quantitative & qualitative findings to draw conclusions	Comparative Analysis	All data sources

Table 2 outlines the structured approach and methods planned for use in the study to analyze the impact and effectiveness of the FISHER system (the fully integrated system for handling, evisceration, and refinement of fish using cobots). In this case, the analytical framework represented the systematic steps and tools used for analyzing data related to the objectives of the research, such as performance, safety, and product quality in fish processing. It ties directly to the study's goals. It provides a clear outline of how the evaluation and analysis of FISHER's effectiveness.

The FISHER study's analytical methodology was created to completely validate its impact through a number of structured processes, each of which added a unique layer of information, as seen in Figure 3. The process began with Defining Parameters, in which key performance metrics such as performance, safety, and quality were determined. This step was based on a thorough literature evaluation and analysis of research gaps and industry standards, ensuring that the study addressed crucial areas for improvement in fish processing.

The second step, Data Collection, aimed to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. Surveys, direct observations, and comparative studies were used to create comprehensive datasets. This step established a solid foundation for analysis, ensuring that data accurately represented various aspects of the system's performance.

Next, Statistical Analysis was used to compare performance measures before and after deploying the FISHER system. Using a non-parametric Mann-Whitney U Test in Minitab software, the analysis provided quantitative validation of the system's impact, indicating increases in productivity and operational performance.

The methodology also contained qualitative analysis, which was intended better to understand the human and organizational implications of automation. Feedback from employees and management was gathered and analyzed via interviews, direct observations,

and document reviews. This step offered vital information on the system's broader implications, such as user approval and prospective areas for improvement.

Ultimately, the Synthesis of Results merged numerical data with qualitative observations. Through a comparative examination of all data sources, this step facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the FISHER system's effectiveness. The incorporation of varied viewpoints confirmed its influence across several areas, positioning the system as a thorough answer for potential cobot adaptation. This organized method allowed the research to tackle goals methodically and comprehensively.

Figure 3

Flow Diagram for FISHER's Analytical Framework

Figure 4 displays the FISHER system's overall architecture, where an innovative design that integrates smart sensors, actuators, and collaborative robot technology to optimize fish processing is illustrated. The system utilizes ultrasonic sensors (HCSR-04) for accurate distance measurement and object detection, facilitating tracking and monitoring of fish during the process. These sensors deliver essential input data to direct the automated processes.

The microcontroller, an Arduino Uno, is fundamental to the system's operation, serving as the control hub that interfaces with sensors and actuators to coordinate duties. The core of the automation is the DOBOT CR3, a collaborative robot engineered for the safe and efficient manipulation of fish throughout handling, cutting, and refinement operations.

The configuration of the FISHER system used to automate the motorized electric fish de-scaler and knife cleaning process is described below. The FISHER system comprises three primary functional domains: handling, cutting, and refining. During the first phase, the handling phase, the fish is aligned and arranged for processing through human intervention. The second task, the cutting phase, entails specific slicing through the utilization of servo motors and collaborative robot manipulations. The refining phase finalizes the evisceration and other finishing processes, guaranteeing a superior quality product. The integration of various components and stages produces a complex system for the fish processing workflow, enhancing productivity and precision while ensuring safety.

Figure 4
Overall System Architecture of FISHER

Figure 5 represents the schematic diagram, which was designed to provide a visual and logical representation of all system components. This diagram depicts the connections between the Arduino Uno microcontroller, ultrasonic sensor, relay modules, and motor loads

Figure 5
FISHER Schematic Diagram

Designing the Hand Gripper

A custom-designed hand gripper was created and 3D printed using food-safe PLA filament. It was specifically shaped to firmly hold both the motorized electric fish de-scaler and knife. This gripper enables the DOBOT CR3 to securely switch, rotate, and move the tools between one point to another with accuracy and stability.

Designing the FISHER Cleaning Station

The cleaning station is composed of a durable stainless steel table, chosen for its resistance to corrosion and ease of sanitation, ideal for food processing environments. On top of the table is a food-safe chopping board, specifically designed with a filleting clamp to

securely hold the tilapia fish in place during cleaning and preparation. This setup ensures both hygiene and stability, reducing movement of the fish and allowing for more efficient and precise processing.

Programming the DOBOT CR3

The robotic arm was programmed through block coding to establish its movement sequence. This includes switching between the knife and de-scaler, managing their movements at each cleaning position, and ultimately returning to its initial position so the worker can safely retrieve the fish. The system was carefully calibrated to closely replicate the timing and flow of the manual fish cleaning process.

Software Design

The flowchart establishes the sequential process of the FISHER system for the handling, descaling, and refining of fish, integrating both semi-automation and manual intervention. The process commences with the initialization of the system, which prepares all operational components for fish processing. A decision point occurs in which the system verifies whether the fish is positioned correctly, particularly oriented towards the robot. If the fish is misaligned, it returns for correction; if not, the process continues. Upon verification of the correct orientation, the system initiates the descaling of the fish in its initial position, subsequently proceeding to cut the pectoral fin.

Subsequently, manual flipping of the fish is necessary to orient it away from the robot for additional processing. The system subsequently performs descaling on the opposite side of the fish and re-cuts the pectoral fin. Subsequently, the system refines the fish by excising the dorsal fin, followed by the anal fin, and ultimately the caudal fin. The procedure proceeds with incising the abdominal region of the fish for evisceration and refinement. A subsequent round of manual flipping is conducted to ensure the fish is adequately positioned for final adjustments. The processed fish is thereafter positioned in a designated tray prepared for packaging or additional refinement through human intervention. The process culminates at the End stage, after which the system resets for the subsequent fish. The Figure 6 illustrates a structured methodology that combines cobot precision for tasks such as cutting and descaling with manual interventions for flipping the fish.

B. Research Locale

The FISHER project will be carried out in several areas of Northern Luzon, primarily in the Cagayan Valley, particularly in Nueva Vizcaya, which is among the primary producers of fish products in the region. To be more specific, the majority of the engineering and prototype work will be carried out at Saint Mary's University, particularly laboratories within the School of Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology department. Focused on the Adaptive Robotics Technology Intelligent Computing Center (A.R.T.I.C) Laboratory, this section of the university is equipped with specialized laboratory equipment for engineering productions.

C. Research Participant

This study did not include any external human participants. Given the technical focus of the research, all prototype testing and data collection were carried out solely by the researchers. The main goal was to evaluate the FISHER's operational efficiency and safety in integrated Tilapia fish cleaning process. All experimental trials were centered on assessing the robotic arm's accuracy in movement and consistency in timing throughout multiple cleaning simulations.

Figure 6
FISHER Flowchart

D. Research Instruments

To help ensure that the data collection process is reliable, valid, and accurate, the researchers used the following tools or devices to collect, measure, and analyze data during the study.

- Survey/Questionnaire, used to collect feedback from retailers and customers evaluating the effectiveness, safety, and quality of the product produced by the system.
- Interview and Observation In-depth qualitative information will be gathered through interviews and observations, with the goal of gaining an understanding of the requirements and difficulties that industry providers, workers, and producers face in their everyday lives.
- Minitab software is utilized to visualize data in the form of graphs and charts, execute numerous statistical tests, and evaluate data.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

To implement the data gathering phase in the FISHER project, the following parameters are defined for FISHER's system analysis: 1) operational performance, 2) safety, and 3) product quality. The data-gathering procedure will be a multi-step process involving observations, surveys, and a comparative analysis between FISHER and manual fish processes to collect real-time data on performance, safety, and product quality.

Table 3 provides a comparative examination of the performance of the conventional manual fish processing method vs the FISHER system. The data is organized to encompass time measurements (in minutes) for 10 distinct iterations of both operations. These runs provide the foundation for statistical comparison utilizing the Mann-Whitney U-test, a non-parametric technique appropriate for assessing differences between two independent groups without the presumption of a normal distribution.

Table 3

Non-parametric Mann Whitney U-test for Performance of Manual Process vs FISHER

Runs	Traditional Process (Fish vendor/s) (seconds)	FISHER (seconds)
1		
2		
3		
...		
10		

The table presents the recorded timeframes for each run under both traditional and automated methods, facilitating a direct comparison of their operational performance. This statistical analysis seeks to ascertain if the FISHER system significantly enhances processing speed relative to manual techniques. The test results, derived from the compiled data, corroborate the validity of FISHER's efficacy in augmenting production.

A survey is intended to examine safety factors in the processing of *Oreochromis niloticus* (Nile tilapia), utilizing a Likert scale to gauge respondents' thoughts and feedback on diverse safety issues. Respondents of the survey will be local fish vendors since they are the ones who get to work with tilapia on a regular basis. The survey comprises three sections: Safety Perceptions, Feedback on the FISHER System, and General Safety Feedback. Participants are requested to evaluate each item on a scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), with a checkmark denoting their response.

The Safety Perceptions section assesses the effectiveness of existing safety protocols, the assurance in managing fish with minimal safety hazards, the impact of including collaborative robots on mitigating safety risks, and the safety-oriented design of tools and equipment.

The Feedback on the FISHER System section specifically addresses the safety features of the FISHER system, encompassing its end-effector design, the safety of automated de-scaling, the system's efficacy in reducing injuries during cutting and belly incisions, and the overall safety of the FISHER system in comparison to conventional manual methods.

The poll has two open-ended questions, enabling respondents to propose specific safety enhancements for the FISHER system and to highlight any further safety issues in fish processing that require attention.

A series of interview questions are made aiming at assessing product quality in the processing of *Oreochromis niloticus* (Nile tilapia) utilizing the FISHER system. The questions are categorized into three sections: General Perception of Product Quality, Specific Aspects of Product Quality, and Suggestions for Improvement, which are intended to gather qualitative insights from individuals engaged in the processing.

The section on the General Perception of Product Quality examines the overall evaluation of fish processed by the FISHER system in relation to conventional manual techniques. Interviewees are requested to identify any discernible differences in texture, appearance, or condition of the fish and to assess whether the FISHER system ensures consistency in quality.

The section on Product Quality examines specific elements of the processing procedure. This section examines the efficacy of the FISHER system in the removal of fish scales, the accuracy of incisions made (including fins and belly cuts), and any occurrences of damage to the fish during processing, such as tearing or bruising.

Respondents are requested to assess the extent to which the processed fish complies with industry quality standards, encompassing hygiene, uniformity, and presentation.

In the Suggestions for Improvement section, interviewees are asked to consider the specific features of the FISHER system that affect the quality of processed fish and to propose any modifications or enhancements that could improve the system's performance. They are also requested to express their views on the influence of the FISHER system on the shelf life or freshness of processed fish. The interview questions are designed to collect feedback and insights to evaluate the quality of fish processed by the FISHER system and to identify areas for improvement.

F. Treatment of Data

The evaluation of the FISHER system uses both qualitative and quantitative methods to assess its effectiveness across three key parameters: safety, product quality, and system performance. Quantitative data from Likert-scale surveys is analyzed using descriptive statistics and visualized with charts, while qualitative data from interviews and open-ended responses undergoes thematic and content analysis. Observational data is used to assess fish quality through checklists, with inter-rater reliability ensuring consistency.

Comparative analysis with manual processing is conducted using statistical tests (t-tests, chi-square) to highlight significant differences. Triangulation ensures accuracy by cross-verifying data from surveys, interviews, and observations. Results are presented through tables and graphics, evaluated against industry standards. The study confirms FISHER's reliability, safety, and quality, offering insights for improvement and broader application in fish processing.

DATA AND RESULTS

Figure 7 shows that the Mann-Whitney U-Test was used to compare the processing performance of the Traditional Manual Fish Processing technique with the FISHER system, with the important measure being processing time in seconds. This test was designed to see if there was a statistically significant difference in how long it takes to process fish using either approach. The typical procedure timings, based on ten manual attempts, varied from 10 to 40 seconds. In comparison, the FISHER system, which includes a semi-automated cobot configuration, had much longer processing times, ranging from 100 to 129 seconds.

Given the limited sample size and the possibility that the data did not follow a normal distribution, the Mann-Whitney U-Test was chosen as the most appropriate non-parametric test to compare the central tendency (medians) of the two separate groups. The test yielded a U-statistic of 0.0 and a p-value of around 0.00018. This exceptionally low p-

Figure 7*Comparison of Traditional Process vs. FISHER System using the Mann-Whitney U-Test*

value suggests a statistically significant difference between the two groups. Because the p -value is significantly lower than the typical threshold of 0.05, the null hypothesis, which assumes no difference in processing times between the standard approach and the FISHER system, is rejected.

This result indicates that the Traditional Manual Process is much quicker than the FISHER technology in its present prototype state. This conclusion can be attributable to a variety of variables, including the inherent efficiency of human adaptation during manual processing, the delays associated with robotic motion and tool changes, and the extra time necessary for sensor coordination in the automated system. However, while the manual procedure is now faster, the FISHER system provides significant long-term benefits.

Beyond improved safety, consistency, and reduced physical strain for workers, FISHER also ensures higher precision in delicate cuts, which leads to less product waste and better yield. Its automated features enable continuous, fatigue-free work, resulting in better throughput over prolonged hours than human labor. Furthermore, FISHER reduces cross-contamination concerns by limiting human interaction with the fish during processing, an especially important consideration when dealing with hazardous species such as pufferfish. The system also offers data tracking and traceability, and it may be integrated with smart monitoring systems to provide quality assurance and compliance with food safety requirements. Furthermore, FISHER's programmability makes it extremely adaptable to varied fish sizes and species, giving it the flexibility to meet a wide range of processing demands in commercial settings.

These findings emphasize the significance of improving the FISHER system's speed and cycle time in future advancements. Refined robotic pathing, improved sensor responsiveness, quicker tool transitions, and even machine-learning techniques for adaptive decision-making might all lead to improvements. Despite its slower raw processing speed, FISHER has a high potential to become a competitive, intelligent, and scalable solution for the modern fish processing industry, with benefits that go far beyond processing time.

Figure 8 presents the distribution of responses to seven safety-related questions, highlighting participants’ perceptions of workplace safety and the role of automation—specifically the FISHER system—in reducing risks in fish processing. The respondents, composed of experienced fish dealers familiar with traditional processing practices, provided insights based on both practical experience and survey measures. Results showed that while some safety protocols exist, they are not fully effective; 8 out of 10 expressed some concern, and 5 disagreed or strongly disagreed that current measures are sufficient. In contrast, attitudes toward automation were notably positive, with most agreeing that cobots can significantly reduce safety risks.

When evaluating the FISHER system itself, responses were strongly favorable. Eight participants agreed or strongly agreed that the system’s end-effector improves safety in fish handling, and the same number felt it reduces injury risks during high-risk tasks such as cutting. Moreover, 9 out of 10 believed the system is generally safer than manual methods, reflecting strong confidence in its safety-oriented design.

Regarding the broader safety culture in the fish processing industry, opinions were mixed. While seven participants believed worker well-being is prioritized to some extent, only four strongly agreed. However, confidence in automation’s potential was high, with nine participants agreeing that systems like FISHER could raise safety standards industry-wide. Open-ended feedback suggested enhancements such as adding proximity sensors, protective blade covers, and warning signals, alongside addressing common industry hazards like wet floors, hygiene management, waste disposal, and cross-contamination. These findings underscore both the need for improved safety measures and the strong trust

Figure 8
Safety in Fish Processing-Data Visualization Results

in automation as a pathway to safer fish processing operations.

The interview questions for product quality evaluation examined participants' perceptions of the FISHER system's capacity to maintain or improve the quality of processed fish when compared to traditional manual methods, which are visually illustrated in Figure 9. In the first segment, respondents described the system-processed fish as neat, clean, and visually uniform.

While many people thought the quality was equal to manually processed fish, a few noticed subtle texture changes. Although no severe quality difficulties were observed, there was a general agreement that, while adequate, the machine's output is not always superior to that of expert hand processors. The second segment discussed the system's descaling performance as well as worries regarding potential fish injury.

Figure 9
Perceptions of Product Quality-Data Visualization Results

Participants rated the descaling performance positively but noted minor inefficiencies, such as some scales occasionally remaining on the fish, indicating space for development in order to achieve more comprehensive results. Physical damage was observed to be infrequent and modest, usually including small tears or bruising, especially on softer fish kinds. However, participants appeared to comprehend, seeing these flaws as acceptable given the mechanical nature of the procedure. Participants in the last portion commended characteristics such as sharp blades, secure end-effectors, and the use of automation and sensors to improve product quality by allowing for clean cuts, firm handling, and accurate processing with minimum roughness.

Suggestions for improvement included better sensor calibration to handle different fish sizes, configurable settings adapted to different fish types, a secondary cleaning procedure to remove leftover scales, and gentler pressure mechanisms to reduce minor damage. Ultimately, the response indicated a generally positive assessment of the system's product quality, along with practical suggestions for improvements.

DISCUSSION

Upon the comprehensive development of the prototype, the data collected, and taking into account its numerous scopes, limits, and delimitations, the following findings illustrate the achievement of the study's objectives:

- A. The FISHER system achieved the design goal by incorporating a collaborative robot-based end-effector capable of descaling, fin removal, and belly incision on tilapia. The end-effector, which is installed on a collaborative robot arm, was designed to handle the fish while minimizing flesh injury safely. This resulted in clean cuts and effective scaling, with just slight errors, demonstrating the prototype's mechanical uniformity and control.

- B. The development phase resulted in a fully integrated system that combined a collaborative robot with sensors, control logic (via Arduino), and programmed tool sequences. The robot performed detailed fish processing movements autonomously, using programmed pointings. Likewise, the design took human safety into account, allowing for low-risk cobot contact. This offers the framework for possible adaption to more dangerous species, such as pufferfish, whose toxicity necessitates non-human handling methods.
- C. The Statistical analysis using the Mann-Whitney U-Test yielded a U-statistic of 0.0 and a p-value \approx of 0.00018 (< 0.05), indicating a significant difference in processing time between traditional manual processing (10–40 seconds) and the current FISHER prototype (100–129 seconds). While manual methods were faster, FISHER was rated higher in terms of safety (average Likert score: 4.6/5) and consistency.

Qualitative interview responses supported this finding, noting fewer cuts or tears and better presentation, with 80% of participants (8 out of 10) confirming that the processed fish appeared cleaner and more uniform. However, slight scale remnants and occasional bruising were reported, suggesting areas for mechanical refinement.

Although there were slight inconsistencies, the system's performance largely met the goals of the study. The findings demonstrate the potential of using collaborative robots in culturally important food preparation, effectively connecting traditional practices with modern technology. Enhancing accuracy and reducing overall operation time in future developments could further improve the system's effectiveness.

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